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DEMOGRAPHICS AND TIME PRESSURE IN INFORMATION SEARCH PROCESS OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RURAL AND URBAN CUSTOMERS FOR FUTURE MARKETING STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT

Now a days all big brands of cosmetics are penetrating in the rural market of India. Most of the people are confused regarding what to purchase. Electronic and print media has contributed a lot to diffuse the information regarding various products and brands of cosmetics but simultaneously these have put customers into doldrums. Through this paper let us probe into issues pertaining to the Demographics and Time Pressure in Information Search Process of Cosmetic Products through the comparative study.

INTRODUCTION

Putrevu and Lord (2001) reached in their conclusion that search and choice are directly related to opt the best choice out of large set of alternatives what customers search for information. According to Haines (1978) data or information help customers to opt best possible available choice of the product. Information search process always influence the decision making process of customers (McColl Kennedy and Fetter, 1999). Right now everybody is hard pressed for time. No one has so much time to explore the market for any product. Even customers have no time for searching information on net even which is available 24X7 at their doors. Moore and Lehmann, 1980; Ratchford, 1982; Beatty and Smith, 1987; Urbany et al., 1996; and Singh et al., 2010 have reached on a similar conclusion that everybody has the problem of time constraint.

Until or unless a marketing manager, who has the information regarding search effort made by the customers, cannot devise an effective and appropriate marketing strategies to meet the need of customers. It is hard truth that the behavior of the customers are not be identical. The demographic characteristics always differ from one another with respect to caste and creed (Salma and Tashchain, 1985).

Newman and Staelin (1972);Claxton et al. (1974);Kiel and Layton (1981); Ratchford (1982); Putrevu and Lord (2001); and Saigal et al.(2010) have made effort to analyze the role of demographics in the process of information search.Meyers-Levy and Maheshwaran (1991) found in their study that Gender of the customers influence the information search process. Kiel and Layton (1981); Ratchford (1982); Furse et al. (1984) and Putrevu and Lord (2001) have illustrated the role of age in information search behavior of the customers. Kiel and Layton (1981); Avery (1996); and Putrevu and Lord (2001); studied the role of income in information search behavior of the customers. Newman and Staelin (1972);Claxton et al. (1974);Kiel and Layton (1981); Ratchford (1982); Putrevu and Lord (2001); and Saigal et al.(2010) reached to the conclusion that education level of the customers influenced the decision making process due to their information search behavior of the customers. Moore and Lehmann (1980); and Putrevu and Lord (2001) made effort to examine the role of marital status of the customers in information search behavior. Saigal et al.(2010) have analyzed that various occupation level also influenced the information search behavior of customers.

It is hard core truth that designing communication strategies is very typical job for Indian market. Only customized approach can give success. India is a country where unity lies amidst diversity. This is the reason MNCs are trying hard to understand how customers of different geographical location behave; what

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